

THE CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE SEEDS OF *SWIETENIA MACROPHYLLA*. PART I. THE NON-BITTER PRINCIPLE

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Two crystalline products have been obtained from the seeds of *Swietenia macrophylla* of which one is bitter and the other, non-bitter. The latter was crystallised from glacial acetic acid [m.p. 256° (decomp.), $C_{18}H_{24}O_6$] and had $[\alpha]_D^{30} = +133.5$ in 4.25% $CHCl_3$ solution. It contains one methoxyl group, one tertiary hydroxyl group and one unsaturated lactone group. On hydrolysis the hydroxy acid of the lactone was obtained. The non-bitter gave a dibromide and on mercuriation a mono-acetoxymercuri derivative of the non-bitter was obtained, along with a dehydro derivative.

Swietenia macrophylla, as well as the closely related *S. Mahogany* (N. O. Meliaceae) are justifiably regarded as very useful timber-trees. That the seeds of these plants, which are borne in large numbers and may be easily collected, contain only bitter or other active principles does not appear to have been observed before. The present series of investigations deals with a bitter and a non-bitter principle from the seeds of the former, and a bitter principle from the seeds of the latter plant. The present paper describes the non-bitter principle of *S. Macrophylla*. The properties of the bitter principle will be reported in the next communication.

A mixture of the bitter and non-bitter principle was isolated from the seeds by a procedure described in the experimental portion. Stirring the dry mixture with small amounts of ether dissolved out the bitter leaving the white non-bitter which was repeatedly crystallised from glacial acetic acid and melted at 256-58° (decomp.). It showed $[\alpha]_D^{30} = +133.5$ in 4.25% solution in chloroform and $[\alpha]_D^{36} = -183.5$ in 2.5% solution in benzene. It did not contain nitrogen, halogen or sulphur.

It gave negative tests for aldehyde, ketone, phenol, methylene-dioxy (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 333), oxycoumarin ether (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 1137), or lactone and an inactive hydroxyl group as well as for unsaturation. Its colour reactions are described in the experimental portion.

The non-bitter may be provisionally called "Swietenin" reserving the name "Swietenolide" or "Swietenolactone" for the bitter principle to be described in Part II. Combustion data indicated a molecular formula of $C_{18}H_{24}O_6$ which was supported by M. W. (Rast) and equivalent weight estimations by lactone titration. The OH group was somewhat inert or 'protected'; the compound was recovered unchanged after mild treatment with acetic anhydride and phenyl isocyanate. On dry heating, a little above the melting point, there was evolution of water and carbon dioxide from the OH and the lactone groups respectively. A similar observation was made by Sircar and Maktader with andrographolide (*loc. cit.*).

Careful acidification of the product, saponified by alcoholic alkali, threw down a mixture of hydroxy acid, "Swietenic-acid", m.p. 208-210° (decomp.) and also a small quantity of a neutral lactone, m.p. 108° (decomp.). The acid was strongly bitter

in taste, unlike the original lactone and did not lactonise easily or gave a positive Legal or Tollen's test, whereas the isomeric lactone was non-bitter and reduced Tollen's reagent.

Swietenin does not decolorise bromine water or potassium permanganate solution at the ordinary temperature and cannot be reduced easily by Adam's platinum catalyst but gives a dibromide with bromine in glacial acetic acid indicating the presence of one double bond. A similar resistance to reduction was shown by Clemo and Cocker in the case of santonins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 33).

During Zeisel determinations of methoxyl group (which gave low value) there was formation of much gummy byproduct with the liberation of some free iodine. An interesting red crystalline iodo derivative was isolated which was apparently formed by the addition of iodine at the double bond with simultaneous replacement of the OH group by the halogen.

Swietenin, dissolved in pyridine, gives a yellow instead of a red solution with Legal's reagent but reduces Tollen's reagent rapidly. Thiele (*Annalen*, 1901, 319, 155) first reported that $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ -lactones immediately reduced Tollen's reagent whereas $\Delta^{\alpha\beta}$ -lactones reduced it slowly or not at all. From a comparative study of a number of cardiac aglucones Jacobs concluded that a positive Legal's test indicated the presence of unsaturation in the $\beta\gamma$ position in the lactone side chain. The test was negative when the unsaturation was removed by reduction or the addition of halogens. In the case of stophanthidine the slow reduction was ascribed by Jacobs to the complexity of the structure. Jacobs also supposed that like Legal's test, Tollen's reaction might be regarded as a sign of $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ -lactone (cf. Jacobs *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1921, 68, 123; 1925, 64, 383; 68, 491; 67, 333; 1926, 70, 1; 1934, 106, 71).

These apparently established views have been disturbed by the more recent evidence derived by Elderfield *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, 6, 273) from the studies of ultraviolet absorption and of hydrogenation experiments on these cardiac genins, which are therefore now supposed to contain the unsaturation in the $\alpha\beta$ position instead. In view of these developments, the interpretation of the results of these two tests must await further observations. The relation between the formation of an 'iso'lactone during hydrolysis and acidification, and the position of the OH group in the molecule will be discussed in the subsequent part.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation and Purification of Swietenin.—The fully matured seeds were dried, decorticated, crushed to a coarse powder and extracted in a copper soxhlet with petroleum ether (b. p. 40°-60°) for 12 to 16 hours. The extract was filtered and on distillation of the solvent it left a thick yellow oil (yield 33%), which was not further investigated. The residue was extracted with chloroform for 16 to 18 hours, the filtered extract much concentrated and poured dropwise to 6-8 times its volume of petroleum ether. A pale yellow flocculent precipitate separated and partly became gummy. The solvent was decanted off and the residue washed twice with the same solvent, and then dried in air overnight. The crude mixture of products was shaken with

small quantities of ether which removed the bitter principle as a yellow solution, which was reserved. The insoluble white residue was repeatedly crystallised from glacial acetic acid and gave fine needles melting at 256-58° (decomp.). They are colorless, odourless and tasteless and practically insoluble in cold or warm water, sparingly soluble in benzene, but more soluble in hot alcohol, ethyl acetate or chloroform, yield about 1%.

A 4.25% solution in chloroform showed $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -133.5$ and a 2.5% solution in benzene showed $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -183.5$.

0.0094 G. of the substance in 0.1213 g. of camphor produced a depression of 9°.16. Molecular weight found was 338.5. Lowering in freezing point in glacial acetic acid gave irregular values. (Found: C, 67.32; H, 7.48. $C_{18}H_{24}O_8$ requires C, 67.5; H, 7.5 per cent).

Hydrolysis.—Swietenin (0.1134 g.) in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for $\frac{3}{4}$ hour with 10 c.c. of *N*/10 (approx.) NaOH with a sodalime guard tube. Titration of the excess of the alkali by 1.076*N*/10 oxalic acid indicated absorption of 3.35 c.c. of the equivalent alkali. (Found: Equiv., 312. $C_{18}H_{24}O_8$ requires equiv., 320).

The hydroxy-acid separated (mixed with a small amount of neutral lactone) on careful acidification in the cold and was purified by dissolving in rectified spirit and pouring into water. It was amorphous and extremely bitter in taste. It gave insoluble Ca, Cu^{++} , Fe^{+++} salts but not Ba or Ca salts, m.p. 208-10° (decomp.). (Found: C, 63.62; H, 7.54. $C_{18}H_{28}O_8$ requires C, 63.9; H, 7.7 per cent). Equivalent wt. found by titration with NaOH was 326. The small amount of the isomeric lactone formed with the hydroxy-acid was not further investigated.

Test for Methoxyl Group.—Swietenin (0.286 g.) was treated with HI (d 1.7) according to Zeisel's method. The recovery of MeI was incomplete. (Found: MeO, 5.25, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{24}O_8$ requires MeO, 9.7 per cent). The dark brown residue in the flask contained free iodine. The mixture was filtered through glass wool and the filtrate poured into water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with thiosulphate, sodium bisulphite and sodium carbonate solutions and evaporated. The brown residue on stirring with alcohol gave red needles which were recrystallised from alcohol. They became yellow at 145° and melted with sublimation and partial decomposition at 250°. The sublimate consisted of red crystals. (Found: I, 55.6. $C_{18}H_{28}O_8I_2$, which may arise by addition of iodine at the double bond and replacement of the OH group by the halogen, requires I, 55.7 per cent).

Unsaturation.—Swietenin (0.1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) and platinised asbestos (0.2 g.) was shaken for 3 hours in an atmosphere of hydrogen at 30°. There was no absorption of the gas and on evaporation of the solvent swietenin was recovered unchanged. Resistance to reduction was also found in the case of santonin by Clemons and Cocker (*loc. cit.*). Swietenin (0.2 g.) in 10 c.c. of glacial acetic acid was treated with bromine in the same solvent at 30° till no more of it was absorbed. After standing overnight the mixture was poured into water, washed by decantation with water containing sulphur dioxide and filtered. The residue was purified by dissolving in

alcohol and pouring into water, m.p. 170° (decomp.). (Found ; Br, 30.7. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 33.3 per cent).

Mercuration.—A mixture of swietenin (0.15 g.) and mercuric acetate (0.4 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid, was heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour at 100° . Mercurous acetate separated and was filtered off after cooling the mixture. The filtrate was poured into water and the white insoluble residue filtered, washed and dried. It was then boiled with benzene and filtered hot. The filtrate on evaporation gave a white gum, which did not contain mercury and was possibly a dehydro compound formed by the oxidising action of the reagent. The compound was dissolved in chloroform and sulphuric acid was added gradually.

On shaking the mixture after two minutes, the sulphuric acid layer became brown and the chloroform layer bluish.

The mercurated residue, insoluble in benzene, melted at $225-27^{\circ}$ (decomp.). Found : Hg, 33.3. Monoacetoxymercuri-swietenin requires Hg, 34.6 per cent).

Colour reactions.—Some colour reactions with reagents for sterols and for cardiac aglucones were carried out with swietenin. The results are set down below :

Rosenheim's reagent	...	No change.
Kohlenberg's reagent	...	No change.
Rosenheim and Callow's reagent	...	Yellow.
Salkoski's reagent	...	Sulphuric acid layer yellow changing to deep brown.
Liebermann Burchard's reagent	...	Yellow ring changing to violet.

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